

The Performance of Technology in Flipped Classrooms for Foreign English Language learners in a Writing Production Course at Universidad Técnica Nacional, San Carlos.

by

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List of Abbreviations

UTN: Universidad Técnica Nacional

EFL: English as a Foreign Language

FC: Flipped Classroom

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Abstract

This case study explores the Performance of Technology in flipped classrooms for foreign English language learners in a writing production course at Universidad Técnica Nacional, San Carlos. This research studied the effects on learners when it comes to writing production. Moreover, it provides proposals for teachers effectively implement the flipped class by using technology. From the qualitative perspective, the methodology includes two stages for the data collection in which applies one interview, and one survey in order to obtain the insight regarding to their performance and perception of the flipped classroom approach in which the finding reveal the positiveness of the Flipped method. Finally, conclusions and recommendations provide information that can help tutors to understand the effects of this approach in young English learners for studying writing production.

Keywords: Flipped classroom, Technology, Foreign Language, Writing techniques.

Chapter I

Introduction

1.1 Problem statement

Throughout the pandemic 2020-2021, it is important to continue preparing learners to be ready for different challenges and for them to know different alternatives for learning a language. For that reason, in different educational centers, they have started to consider the use of technological tools to support their learning education process to minimize the impact of the pandemic. According to Karp and Fletcher (2014) if the technology is used efficiently, they have the potential to help learners and their education centers by contributing to enhance the performance and the results when learners feel guided and supported.

But the question is what are learners looking for in these days to find out the perfect university to study according to the American Association of community colleges (2014) learners are not only looking for a traditional college experience a place where they can feel that they are learning and they are having the opportunity to grow up as professional; they are looking for the opportunity to have balance of work and family that they learner loans are not that expensive and the customized learning experiences and the opportunity to learn as much as possible.

According to Flores (2019) the virtual platform called Aula Virtual UTN has been opened to professors for training courses to enhance the technological and pedagogical Skills in their teaching areas. However, before 2020 it was mainly used for professors and now due to the virus Covid-19 learners have to use it. Flores (2019) states that Universidad

Técnica Nacional is looking for a better or learning experience to enhance their learning process. Yushau (2006) states that the technology tools are simply new gadgets to improve the way people learn and they cannot replace the traditional teaching and learning model.

Consequently, the flipped classroom model of teaching is an outgrowth of interactive personal technologies. The flipped classroom model was defined by Bretzmann (2013) as a process of making learners watch video lectures at home and later doing the work and activities in class. Bergmann and Sams (2012) are pioneers of using the flipped classroom model in their high school classes. Bergmann and Sams describe the flipped classroom concept simply as “that which is traditionally done in class is now done at home, and that which is traditionally done as homework is now completed in class” (p. 13).

The flipped classroom is featured by tutors focusing on higher levels, as the one being studied in Universidad Técnica Nacional, learners that are creative in the classroom where there is a learner-centered approach, and they have the opportunity to put into practice what they have learned as much as possible outside the classroom. (Bergman & Sams (2012), Bretzmann (2013)).

The writing skill is a complex process because it needs the skillful coordination of both cognitive and linguistic processes and resources in learners according to (Hayes 1996 and Kellogg 1996). The things that in higher levels Learners have to work on our things like planning and organizing having supporting ideas main ideas and basic poems like spelling punctuation, word choice can be a difficult task (Richards and Renandya, 2002). For writing production, it is necessary to have time to organize ideas and feelings about a certain topic. English learners need time to find the ideas they need and the way the want to express them. For that reason, a flipped lesson can free you from the distractions of your personal life. Writing from a place where you can control your time and organize your thoughts without having the pressure of classmates and teachers allows you to clear your mind and focus on the task at hand.

With all that being said, the combination of flipped classroom and writing in education seemed like a new way to expand into the heart of creativeness and willingness

to learn. Ideas and freedom can only be found in places where learners feel secured. Having to deal the pressure of writing in class to hand in a script is not a good practice.

In the present research paper, we study the Performance of Technology in flipped classrooms for foreign English language learners in a writing production course at Universidad Técnica Nacional, San Carlos.

1.2 Background to the study:

In the world, teachers have been constantly looking for a way to engage learners into study outside the classroom, a resource that helps teachers to achieve this goal is flipped classroom which Alvarez (2011) describes a flipped classroom as a teaching methodology in which practice exercises and assignments that are usually completed by learners at home in a regular classroom are done during class under the individual guidance of the teacher.

Lesson explanations, lectures, worksheets, and practices which normally would be done during class with the professor answering questions and providing feedback has been replaced for interactive platforms " the emergence of flipped learning environment are driving by changes in educational practice" (Zitter & Hoeve, 2012, p. 5). Learners find extra material and all the practices and support materials; they need to complete the assigned tasks.

It is important to say that flipped classroom has different effects on learners and that it could induce an additional demand on students as it increases the appeal on the self-regulated learning capabilities of students. Whereas some researchers presume that this may lead to positive effects in terms of learning outcomes and self-regulated learning

capabilities of students; however, others hypothesize that student's lacking self-regulated learning capabilities could experience disadvantages in a flipped classroom (Alter, et al., 2019).

Some effects can be categorized in three stages according to Alter, Phielix, Janssen & Kester (2019) the First, conveying information and instruction through conventional lectures in the traditional classroom has its shortcomings, because the teacher delivers the instructional message in a one-size-fits-all manner and the possibilities for the students to interact with the teacher during the lecture (e.g., to ask or answer questions) are limited. This might lead to a lack of student engagement and it might hamper students to actively construct knowledge. Furthermore, this should not imply that teachers should stop giving direct instruction. In a FC approach, then, learners receive information and instruction before class, for example, through video lectures. This has the advantage that learners are able to control the viewing frequency and viewing pace of the instruction material before class.

The second, learners in traditional classrooms independently work on homework assignments to apply the information and instruction that was presented to them in lectures. From a cognitivist perspective, however, a lack of direct instructional guidance during application might result in cognitive overload and hinders students to store knowledge in their long-term memory. In a FC, nevertheless, learners can devote classroom time to learning activities focused on applying the instructional material (such as working through problems and engaging in collaborative learning) with the guidance of the teacher.

Finally, in the third one, learners are better able to achieve higher learning outcomes, as there is more classroom time available for learning activities that foster active, constructive, and interactive engagement modes. In contrast, in a traditional classroom most classroom time is devoted to activities such as lectures, with mostly a passive mode of engagement.

Khan (2012) emphasizes that all learners learn and concentrate in different ways and at different times. Therefore, it is the responsibility of teachers to provide the opportunity to

their learners to study at a time and place that best meets their learning styles in an attempt to personalize their lessons as much as possible.

1.3 Justification

In order to know the effects of flipped classroom in the learners whether if it is a positive or negative effect a research done by Strayer (2007) says that the advantages of flipped classroom model have two key components: the first one is the educational technology, and the second one is the activity Learning.

Both influence the learning process environment and with teachers get to support and guide the learners to watch lessons by using technology for educational purposes and once they have learned what is necessary, they go to the class and they perform the tests and complete the activities and exercises by having the help of the teacher. According to Lage, Platt, and Treglia (2000) a Flipping classroom means that events that have traditionally taken place inside of the classroom; now are taking place outside of the classroom. Bretzmann (2013) thinks that a flipped classroom must be seen as a process and not a procedure because according to Findlay- Thompson and Mombourquette (2014) there is a philosophy behind the flipped classroom teaching methodology is that tutors can teach both content and process.

The writing skill is a complex process because it needs the skillful coordination of both cognitive and linguistic processes and resources in learners according to (Hayes 1996 and Kellogg 1996). The things that in higher levels Learners have to work on our things like planning and organizing having supporting ideas main ideas and basic poems like spelling punctuation, word choice can be a difficult task (Richards and Renandya, 2002). For writing production, it is necessary to have time to organize ideas and feelings about a certain topic. English learners need time to find the ideas they need and the way the want to express them. For that reason, a flipped lesson can free you from the distractions of your

personal life. Writing from a place where you can control your time and organize your thoughts without having the pressure of classmates and teachers allows you to clear your mind and focus on the task at hand. As an educator, the flipped method using technology for writing course fits the model that UTN looks in its students to have since its foundation in 2008 which is an educational model, innovative and creative: a technical university that integrates the various levels and stages of technical education and higher studies, demanded by the country, in a single continuous and comprehensive educational process, that also allowed adequate training, required by the needs of national development and that managed to meet the challenges in Costa Rica (Rodriguez, n.d).

The education model in UTN is holistic which Universidad Técnica Nacional (2015) defines as the educational practices at UTN which promote the critical and creative thinking; also, the development of leaders committed to society, whose training is contextualized from interdisciplinary studies, transdisciplinary experiences and projects that facilitate understanding, reflection, and innovative responses. Moreover, the integration of teaching and learning, the complete integration in that process; this requires that from educational management, the learner is supported, by offering him new alternatives, possibilities and challenges that stimulate the learner in the search for information and the construction of new knowledge, through collaborative learning strategies, inter-learning, and self-management of learning.

As mentioned, that before, there are different situations that learners have to deal with when they are learning and practicing their writing a skill for that reason researchers who have been looking for Effective techniques to teach writing have found the flipped learning approach. It is also said that the flipped classroom is a personalized learning in which the learner is the protagonist, and the learner has the opportunity to construct their own knowledge. Learners view and review the materials and they can learn at their own pace and according to their own needs. (Basal, 2015).

1.4 Purpose Statement

The purpose of this study is to know the performance of technology in flipped classrooms for foreign English language learner in writing production courses at the Universidad Técnica Nacional in San Carlos Costa Rica where the Customer Service English program implemented the flipped classroom with the purpose of learning writing production techniques, which is developed in lessons to enhance the learning process of English as a foreign language.

1.5 Research questions

- What are the effects of technology in Flipped classrooms when learning English writing?
- Do English learners increase their writing production when having flipped classroom?
- Is technology increasing in the learners the writing production during flipped classrooms?
- Do English learners study more English topics when having a flipped classroom?

1.6 Delimitations

This research work is proposed to be carried out in San Carlos, at Universidad Técnica Nacional which is one of the five public universities of Costa Rica. The scope of the study will be limited to a group of English learners of the English for customer service

program that have been learning writing techniques along the past months and now have changed to flipped classroom.

The participants of this study are 10 higher education learners . They are studying English to enhance their writing production skills; therefore, ten people will be participating in this research project.

1.7 Definition of terms

Flipped classroom:

Alvarez (2011) describes a flipped classroom as a teaching methodology in which practice exercises and assignments that are usually completed by learners at home in a regular classroom are done during class under the individual guidance of the teacher.

Writing process:

According to Hyland's proposal (2003) shows a model for implementing the writing process in learners. It is basically the topic selection it can be by teachers or learners , then they prewriting they can use some brainstorming or data collection outlining and highlighting, then composing in this part getting ideas and paper and gather everything, next responding to draft from the professor or the other learners, after that revising which is about reorganizing and adjusting the content to the audience; responding to their friends advice is to improve their organization and the style and then finally, proofreading and editing just to check out a form in the layout. the other part would be the evaluation, and the follow-up tasks for General Improvement.

Foreign language:

According to Punchihetti (2013) What is termed a 'foreign language' is a language which has generally no direct link with the person's immediate social or personal environment. The selection of a target foreign language is thus largely a personal choice of the learner, except in cases where children and adults are compelled to learn foreign languages for academic or professional reasons.

Technology self-efficacy:

It is defined as "The user's personal confidence toward successfully and purposefully using the technology itself" (Holden & Rada, 2011, p. 353).

Chapter II

Literature review

2.1 Introduction

Education has evolved along the years now the technology has become an important part of the daily basis on a classroom. Valdez (2005) said that the use of the Technology in the classroom everyday activities in not an occasional activity that teachers put into practice. The technology has helped different schools to start new programs and to educate the learners . Due to the pandemic (2019) changes lately implementation of a flipped classroom by using technology seems like a possible solution. The purpose of this research paper is to study the effects of the technology in flipped classroom for foreign English language learners when they are learning writing production techniques in classes.

In a flipped classroom the learner is the protagonist the process and they have the opportunity to put into practice everything that they have learned outside the classroom. Bretzmann (2013) said that the flipped lesson is a model of teaching and outgrowth interactive personal technology for everyone, therefore the effects that he has over the writing production techniques will be explored and analyzed throughout this paper. The results from this study will give administrative and professors the information to put into practice this model and flipped and technology-based classroom. and this chapter the theoretical framework is for this to study and provided a review for literature has been analyzed to study and examine the effects all learners of a writing production techniques class by implementing the method of flipped classroom

a. The technology in a flipped classroom:

Due to the new era of Education the use of Technology has become one of the techniques to teach in a new reality. That are programs in schools that are using the technology to teach a lesson. Technology has a role on the flipped classrooms nowadays because the closest way to except they variety of technologist in order to have a positive result from the different sources provided by teachers and tutors. The significance of the technology acceptance suggests that learners would be willing to use various technologies if they thought there would be a positive outcome linked to using the technology. Instructors and learners who see that there are positive benefits in using technology may be more willing to use the technologies. The technology acceptance model is an intention-based model developed purposely for explaining and/or predicting user acceptance of computer technology (Hu, Chau, Sheng, & Tam, 1999). Besides, Waxman et al. (2003) stated that research has determined that the implementation of technology into the classroom has a constructive effect on learner academic growth compared with the traditional classroom model. In fact, Ross et al. (2003) found that learners who used laptops scored higher than learners who did not use a laptop on writing activities for the class. Learners who used a laptop also scored significantly higher on five of the seven sections of a problem-solving exercise designed specifically for the study. Moreover, a research carried out by O'Dwyer et al. (2005) pointed out that when technology is used differently, the results of learner growth are totally different from the ones expected.

Also, research papers have discussed the effects of using technology to provide instructions and guides for the quality and the number of words that Learners have to use in writing papers. For instance, a research carried out in Middle School learners and High School learners that were using word processors like computers the Learners that where using those devices were able to produce longer passages while also having a good quality in the passages then those learners who were just using a paper and pencil , for this reason there was a positive effect on the learners that were writing in the technological devices. (Goldberg, Russell, & Cook, 2003; Kulik, 2003).

b. The flipped classroom model:

Researchers along the years have been investigating the effect of flipped classroom in the learner's performance, researchers in fact have said that this model increases the academic growth in learners. (Bergmann & Sams, 2012; Lage et al., 2000; Strayer, 2007). Others like Marcey and Brint (2012) were working in the flipped classrooms effect in the University in California, where in one of the groups of undergraduate introductory course they are implementing the flipped classroom method. Marcey and Brint stated that the flipped class had better results in all tests and quizzes that were doing at a time.

In other research, learners of 12th grade were in different interaction courses, and most of the class were using the traditional method and while only one classroom was using the flipped method, at the end of the study the outcomes from the flipped classroom were higher than the other courses. All the content was taught simultaneously therefore they did not have advantage over any other course. (Day and Foley 2006).

However, in a high school in the state of Michigan some classrooms were implementing the flipped method and the performance in task instead of increase, it decreased (Finkel, 2012). Another study was carried in by Johnson (2000) using high schoolers and the research indicated that learners did not improve at all, even though they were using technology once a week they did not show any improvement in their academics.

Likewise, in 2005, the Freedom to Learn program was implemented in 195 Michigan schools for 1 year. The program implemented in this educational center was looking forward to improving the academic growth by putting into practice the technology during the flipped classrooms. The results of the program indicated no significant gain in the learners' writing, English, reading, and math scores (Lowther, Strahl, Inan, & Bates, 2007). For that reason, others like Zacharis (2010), believe that learners in traditional learning groups had higher, but not statistically significant, levels of academic growth over

the online learning groups that were implementing flipped classrooms by using the technology.

c. Writing techniques: Implementation of flipped classrooms in writing courses

Writing is one of the most important skills when learning English as a foreign language. Writing has the power of learners to master the right into mix, therefore learners need to be aware of the writing process and the product that they are looking for to obtain. Learning writing includes the learning process but it also includes the power of knowing how to control and manage the word and the expressions that we want to put into paper. One of the main objectives of the Strategic writing is that they learning to ride includes the learning of mental procedures to produce writing and in order to control the production of the writing. (Calhoun & Hale, 2003). Different researchers have indicated that for effective writers the way of writing has to be strategic. The meaning of strategic writing techniques has to do with the adjustment and the purposes for each writing tasks. Strategic writers have a variety of a strategies and the skills as they construct paragraphs. (Buhrke, Henkels, Klene, & fister, 2002).

A strategy is a plan selected by the writer who is looking for a particular objective due to the need of a written paper in order to finish a task. (El-Koumy, 1991). The main objective of writing instructions is to help learners to become better writers, hence the Learners can achieve autonomy and if they are writing papers and they use the correct strategies when it comes to production. It is strategic writing is essential for constructing meaning in learners writing and to motivate them to write and get the positive results from it (Okasha,& Hamdi 2014). Many English foreign language learners say that writing is eye complex skill to deal in language. In the same way, teachers also say that it's difficult to assess learners in the writing test in providing feedback to all of them in equality academic course. (Abdel-Hack, 2002).

According to Calhoun & Hale, (2003) all the researchers indicated that the Strategic in writing is a thinking procedure for producing writing which is part of the cognitive part

and to control the production which is part of the metacognitive. the Strategic writing is a link between cognitive and metacognitive there is knowledge associated with the thinking skill. Finally, strategic writing shows how to discover their idea in a strategic method. Learners learn the strategy required to develop an ability and to create different and Future Works which that is a successful is technique that requires mental discipline, flexibility, and creative thinking which requires time and peace to work. (Okasha,& Hamdi 2014).

When it comes to peace and time to work the flipped classroom seems to be the answer, for instance the researchers Leis, Tohei, and Cooke (2015) compared a traditional English composition course with the other using the flipped method with 22 Japanese university learners. The results showed that those studying under the flipped method produced a significantly higher number of words in essays. In addition, the participants who received the flipped method resulted in significantly greater improvements in their writing proficiency.

Moreover, in the investigation done by Ahmed (2016) explored the effect of a flipping classroom on writing skill in the EFL context of Saudi Arabia with 60 female university learners (30 in flipped classroom and 30 in the control group). The flipped learning group was significantly better than the control group. Furthermore, the participants who experienced flipped learning have positive attitudes towards it.

d. The positive and negative effects of technology in Flipped Classrooms

The flipped classroom model is an educational model that it has advantages and disadvantages for learners. They flipped classroom education model it promotes the ability to socialize through different online programs it also has to do with the contact with teachers and other learners where they interaction is promoted and in a way is intended to

allow teachers to have the time to address real-world problems and by solving and thinking. It allows learners through prioritize the family time and the values concerning to pace and Tasks. It also allows learners to have the responsibility of their own education. Advances in general in educational technology have an important role in the emerging interest of the flipped classroom methodology. According to Strayer (2011), Through years there has been increase in the use of technology in the schools and for that reason the availability of online programs and stuff worse to every learner has let the the flipped classroom is successful.

As of 2011, there were more than 2,400 online video lessons for teachers and learners to utilize on the Khan Academy site, and the percentage of Internet users increased by 15% from 2007 to 2010 (Strayer, 2011). Teachers and part of committees from different schools have to decide whether to use technology within schools and to perform different activities in which everyone has access to the different tools and sources posted in the media. For that reason, Bishop and Verleger (2013), say that free softwares Technologies are related to the growing interest on the flipped classroom models because the free softwares have helped to eliminate some Financial barriers that in some schools that was a problem. Technology is making education more time effective and it has got into the core of the houses of different learners in each place thanks to the different platforms that are being used nowadays.

In a flipped classroom setting, learners can learn the skill, research it, practice it, and complete assignments even before entering class. Varying levels of learners could be accommodated within the flipped classroom model. The instructor would have more time to accommodate the varying levels and also have the opportunity to implement differentiated podcasts for their struggling learners. The benefit of this would be that there is not a time limit on the initial instruction, thus a learner that might learn at a slower rate than their peers would have lots of time to understand a concept, research it, and practice it without feeling rushed. This would allow them extra time for more mastery, group, and lab practices. (Bishop and Verleger 2013)

In a study about the Effects of flipping the classroom on learning outcomes and satisfaction Alter, Phielix, Janssen & Kester (2019) categorized the effects in different stages:

First, conveying information and instruction through conventional lectures in the traditional classroom has its shortcomings, because the teacher delivers the instructional message in a one-size-fits-all manner and the possibilities for the students to interact with the teacher during the lecture (e.g., to ask or answer questions) are limited. This might lead to a lack of student engagement and it might hamper students to actively construct knowledge. Though, this should not imply that teachers should stop giving direct instruction. In an FC approach, therefore, students receive information and instruction before class, for example, through video lectures. This has the advantage that students are able to control the viewing frequency and viewing pace of the instruction material before class. In this way, cognitive load could be reduced as learner-controlled video segments are better able to support learners processing the learning material.

It is important to consider that a flipped classroom could induce an additional demand on learners as it increases the appeal on the self-regulated learning capabilities of students. While some researchers presume that this may lead to positive effects in terms of learning outcomes and self-regulated learning capabilities of learners, others mention that learner's lacking self-regulated learning capabilities could experience disadvantages in a flipped classroom.

Second, students in traditional classrooms independently work on homework assignments to apply the information and instruction that was presented to them in lectures. From a cognitivist perspective, however, a lack of direct instructional guidance during application might result in cognitive overload and hinders learners to store knowledge in their long-term memory. In a flipped classroom, however, learners can devote classroom time to learning activities focused on applying the instructional material (such as working through problems and engaging in collaborative learning) with the guidance of the teacher. From an educational psychological perspective, this is beneficial for learning because learning happens when the learner is actively generating meaning, instead of passively

receiving information, in fact, our mind actively and dynamically constructs meaning by building relations with prior knowledge. In the flipped classroom, this learning process is guided by the teachers. Students in a traditional classroom lack this guidance when they engage in similar activities during homework assignments after class.

Third, learners can achieve deeper understanding of the learning material as they become more engaged. In an FC approach, students are better able to achieve higher learning outcomes, as there is more classroom time available for learning activities that foster active, constructive, and interactive engagement modes. In contrast, in a traditional classroom most classroom time is devoted to activities such as lectures, with mostly a passive mode of engagement.

Fourth, as compared to traditional classrooms, FC allows more classroom time for students to interact with their teacher(s) and peers, and to engage in learning activities which are differentiated based on their capabilities and needs. Classroom interaction enhances learner relatedness stimulates collaborative learning and offers students the opportunity to receive support from their teacher or peers when applying knowledge during class. For instance, an essential component of a teacher's role in an active learning classroom (i.e., a classroom in which learners engage in learning activities instead of passively listening) is to provide feedback to students to guide and facilitate learners' learning processes. Thus, in a flipped classroom, there may be more room for students to receive effective feedback and differentiated instruction from their teacher.

Finally, FC is often assumed to be a promising pedagogical approach that increases student satisfaction about the learning environment; however, mixed results about learners' attitudes towards FC; in general, learners were positive about the learning environment, but a few studies showed opposite results. From a theoretical perspective, we can say that a flipped classroom approach is able to satisfy students' needs for competence, autonomy, and relatedness and, thus, entice greater levels of motivation

Overall, along the review of the literature to explore the performance of Technology in flipped classrooms for foreign English language learners when learning writing production techniques, the outcomes might vary due to the technological interaction to increase the writing production in learners by using different strategies. In general, the perception obtained from the authors is that learners when using computer-aided instruction were more positive than classrooms that offered little or no technology.

e. How to implement the flipped model

Dunn (2014) has written a short piece on “The 6-step guide to flipping your classroom”, which presented 6 easy steps for implementing flipped classroom.

As first step we have, Plan, you must figure out which lesson in particular you want to flip. Outline the key learning outcomes and a lesson plan. Subsequently, record some parts instead of teaching this lesson in-person, make a video. A screencast works. Make sure it contains all the key elements you would mention in the classroom, therefore in case of questions they can always replay the video for better understanding. In Bergmann and Sams’ book (2012), they also pointed out that do not make a video just for the sake of making a video. Only do so when you feel these are appropriate and necessary. It all depends on the educational goal of the lesson. When you have the video completed and reviewed, share it with your students, make it engaging and clear. Explain that the video’s content will be fully discussed in class. This will upgrade their learning process and will motivate them to the use of technology in flipped lesson, now that your students have viewed your lesson, they’re prepared to actually go more in-depth than ever before.

Moreover, we can team up our students to create activities in groups, this is an effective way to discuss the topic is to separate into groups where students are given a task to perform. They will talk about your previous video or simple complete a task or practice once they fully understand the topics. Furthermore, you can regroup them one more time. This consists in getting the class back together to share the individual group’s work with everyone. For instance, ask questions, dive deeper than ever before to get the results expected.

Moreover Dunn (2014) mentioned some other strategies that can be used in in-class activities include:

Active learning allows students to apply concepts in class where they can ask peers or instructors for feedback and clarification. Another one is Peer instruction. Students can teach each other by explaining concepts or working on small problems. In the other hand we have, Collaborative learning. Collaborative learning activities could increase student engagement, enhance student understanding, and promote collective intelligence. And the two last ones are problem-based learning and Discussions or debate. Class time can be spent working on problems that can last for the duration of a semester, also giving students the opportunity to articulate their thoughts on the spot and to develop their arguments in support of their opinions or claims.

Students' perception of flipped classroom strategy

In a research carried out by Shih, W.-L., & Tsai, C.-Y. (2017) students perceived that the flexible environments in the flipped classroom provided them with multiple learning vehicles and opportunities for learning-by-doing. For the learner-centered approach, the students in this study expressed that they learned a lot from the learner-centered activities. Students' shift from passive to active learning constitutes the key to a successful flipped class that was experimented by the students of this research. For the intentional content, students expressed the belief that the materials on the online platform were too numerous and varied, and they felt reluctant to undertake preclass preparation. It may be that an excessive amount of teaching materials causes an excessive cognitive load. Teachers' professional roles are more crucial in flipped learning and students need to be guided into the correct perspectives in order to increase their willingness to cooperate. It is vital for any course to choose wisely the resources and the

amounts to enhance the use of technology during the inverted lessons. Shih, W.-L., & Tsai, C.-Y. (2017) also added as a suggestion that instructors may explain the purpose of the flipped classroom to students and convey to them that they should be responsible for their own learning. Another aspect of the performance from the students was the little interaction with the material provided before class because they were used to the traditional method for studying Chen et al. (2014) and Findlay-Thompson and Mombourquette (2014) also identified the same situation and remarked that students' workloads are heavier due to homework outside of the classroom. This may pose a challenge to implementing flipped classrooms (Chen & Chen, 2015). Moreover, students perceived the advantage of group discussion but indicated that some difficulties occurred during cooperative learning of in-class learning activities. For progressive learning networking activities, online discussions during the post class activities can also bring students closer to the teacher and their classmates and encourage them to participate for team learning. Findlay-Thompson and Mombourquette (2014) also found that participatory activities during class provide students with opportunities to be involved in-class activities that can improve their practical competencies. For engaging and effective learning experiences, hands-on activities and in-class cooperative learning can help strengthen team cooperation (Chen & Chen, 2015; Chen et al., 2014), furthermore; researchers stated that students engaged in in-class and post class activities. They responded to the different learning approach and were glad to participate in the hands-on activities. For a diversified and seamless learning platform, students' preexisting learning behaviors and interests should be taken into consideration when preparing online teaching according to the research of Shih, W.-L., & Tsai, C.-Y. (2017).

EFL students' learning outcomes in a blended learning environment

According to Peng and Fu (2021) students' learning outcomes in blended learning involve two aspects: improvement in English linguistic competence and psychological

development of English learning. In addition, blended learning facilitates students' listening, speaking, reading, writing and vocabulary development, which echoes previous research findings that implementing blended learning in language courses can significantly improve students' writing knowledge and skills (Shih, 2011; Zheng, 2019) by employing Internet-based learning platforms (e.g., small private online courses, MOOCs, Edmodo) and social media tools such as Facebook and WordPress. Meanwhile, EFL students' learning autonomy, confidence, perseverance and satisfaction are enhanced in a blended learning environment, which is consistent with research that students have greater autonomy in blended learning and they are satisfied with this particular learning model, which prompts greater student perseverance and confidence (Jia et al., 2012; Zhang & Han, 2012). Furthermore, Peng and Fu (2021) also stated that the results of the descriptive analysis indicate that students' English vocabulary improves the most in blended learning. This suggests that the blended learning model can substantially increase students' vocabulary knowledge by integrating online vocabulary assessment system with face-to-face teaching. Likewise, the results could be associated with students' learning habits.

Several studies across a range of disciplines at tertiary institutions have shown promising results with the use of a flipped approach. In some cases, it has been found to produce improved learning outcomes said Peng and Fu (2021), and in many cases it has led to greater student satisfaction (e.g., Enfield, 2013; McGivney-Burelle & Xue, 2013). First, as most of the studies investigating students' learning performance mentioned, flipping the class is a way to improve learning performance. Students particularly welcomed the fact that they had access to materials like video lectures, and they were able to prepare themselves and even learn when, where, and at the pace they wanted; students welcomed their ability to learn independently. Second, more than half the studies analyzed suggest that students have very positive attitudes toward the flip classroom approach, describing the approach as useful, helpful, and flexible. Third, a number of papers indicated high levels of engagement. Based mostly on qualitative data and instructors' observations, it is stated that even if the performance is sometimes low, student engagement remains at a high level. Fourth, it is found that there is a measurable increase in the quantity of

discussions, although the quality of discussions was not assessed in the collected studies. Fifth, flipped classrooms force students to work collaboratively, and qualitative evidence indicate that students improved their cooperative skills.

It has been suggested that students' increased ownership of self-paced work, including notetaking from videos and responding to questions, can contribute to learning outside class (Davies et al., 2013; Enfield, 2013). Inside class, learning may be improved through a greater emphasis on active learning, including problem solving, as well as teachers' ability to focus on students who need extra help (Davies et al., 2013; McGivney-Burelle & Xue, 2013). Moreover, Enfield (2013) has found an improvement in students' self-efficacy in regard to independent learning through participation in a flipped approach and considers that such an approach may help prepare students for twenty-first century careers.

Chapter III

Research Design

3.1. Research Paradigm

In this study, the researching paradigm applied is the interpretivist because the research is qualitative. Thanh & Thanh (2015) said that the interpretivist paradigm: “allows researchers to view the world through the perceptions and experiences of the participants” (p. 24).

Since the study will be studying the effect of a phenomenon and try to describe it, the research will be exploratory and by the end the outcomes obtained will be analyzed in order to know the effects. The research uses the qualitative approach due to the core of the investigation which seeks to find out what are the effects of the technology in flipped classroom for foreign English language learners when they are learning writing production techniques in classes. According to Denzin and Lincoln (2005)

Qualitative research is a situated activity that locates the observer in the world. It consists of a set of interpretive, material practices that make the world visible. They turn the world into a series of representations, including field notes, interviews, conversations, photographs, recordings, and memos to self.

Moreover, this research studies the performance produced by the technology in blended learning. Although the study analyzes and describes the experiences from the participants answers, it also includes some numerical data collected in a Likert scale, the final outcomes combined the information gather for interpretation of the effects.

3.2. Research Approaches

The research approach for this study is the case study. Gerring (2004) proposes the following definition for the case study:

I propose to define the case study as an intensive study of a single unit for the purpose of understanding a larger class of (similar) units. A unit connotes a spatially bounded phenomenon-e.g., a nation-state, revolution, political party, election, or person-observed at a single point in time or over some delimited period of time.

3.3 Context of Study and Participants

The stakeholders of this research are current learners from at Universidad Técnica Nacional in the of Quesada San Carlos. The Universidad Técnica Nacional (UTN) is one of the five public universities in Costa Rica. The participants of this research are enrolled in the English for customer service program that lasts ten months divided in bimesters which they have to approve in order to continue. The participants of this research attend classes twice a week for 3 hours. Due to the pandemic, learners are experiencing virtual classes. For material and content learners use the platform Aula Virtual UTN in which they can find all related to the program in each bimester. For the lectures, learners join in every class to google meets where the method of flipped classroom is being implemented. Learners take advantage of the time provided in the lecture to clarify doubts and receive feedback from the tutor in charge and classmates.

The program of English for customer service seeks to build professional that are able to communicate in English written and conversational. For that reason, learners must have time to develop different types of written documents. Moreover, learners work with content topics from Interchange books and British council in which they have the opportunity to acquire the input for delivering the tasks assigned by the professor. The learners did not know each other before the English course, and they are from different neighborhoods in Quesada. The learners share in common that all them want to learn and

improve their writing techniques in order to perform at their work. The participants have had the opportunity to travel to English speaking countries or studied in bilingual high schools of Quesada, therefore their level of English is adequate for the English program they are taking.

3.4. Rationale for selection

The rationale for choosing the participants was the willingness of the learners to be part of a research project due to their positive attitude and commitment with the investigation. The learners state the importance of generating data by being tested and analyzed to improve the education and the implementation of different methods to enhance the education and strategies in the English programs at Universidad Técnica Nacional.

3.5. Instrumentation

For this case study during the first stage, the participant had an online interview (See appendix B) with the researchers in which they answered different questions regarding their experience in flipped classroom in UTN using the technology for writing production courses.

In the second stage of the case study, the participants will answer a survey (See appendix C) about the outcomes and learning experience of the research activities.

3.6. Data Collection

This research paper collected the data in two stages and using quantitative and qualitative methods different instruments were used while developing the study. In the first

stage, a focus group was developed to know general information like age, educational background, English studies prior university among others, as well as the student's perception toward the effects of blended learning and the use of technology for writing courses.

During the second stage, a survey was carried out to find the effects about the . For this section a Likert scale was applied through google forms, in this survey the participants answered questions about the learning process with the effects of technology in the flipped classroom and their level of satisfaction with the approach developed. Both instruments were applied online due to the pandemic.

3.7. Research Variables

Figure 1

Research variables

No.	Variable	Definition	Operational definition
1	Writing production	The production of sentences, paragraphs, stories and essays and other written documents.	The skill studied during the course was writing. The outcome can be different with speaking or listening.
2	Gender	Participants are male or female.	A gender can define the commitment and positivism toward the approach.
3	Technology	The tool for sharing different kind of media information digitally.	The effects in the learning process with technology can affect the level of understanding and engagement.
4	Flipped	An approach in which the class are inverted.	The flipped method varies from the traditional method.

5	Effect	A consequence derived from flipped approach or cause.	The effects can be positive or negative depending the results.
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3.8. Ethics and Consent Form

In order to fulfill the standard ethic requirements, the participant was provided with a written consent form (See Appendix A) that provided both information about the research project as well as the participant's willingness to participate in the project.

Chapter IV

Findings and discussion

4.1. Participants' background information

The total of participants for collecting the data were 10 people. However, only three people participated in the focus group which consisted in nine opened questions (see Appendix B).

Figure 2.

Sociodemographic information of participants

Demographic	Value	Quantity
Gender	Male	6 participants.
	Female	4 participants.
Age	16 – 25 years old	7 participants.
	26-35 years old	3 participants.
Focus group: interview	3 responses to 9 questions.	3 participants.
Survey: Likert scale	10 responses to 10 questions.	10 participants.

Note. sociodemographic information, the value, and the quantity of participants.

a. Focus group

In questions 1 and 2, the Participant A is 34 years old, he is an agronomist and he had studied English in high school and when he studied agronomy. Participant B is 26 years old, and he is an administrator, he also studied English in high school and college.

Participant C is 27 years old; he is an engineer and he studied English in elementary and high school and during his major years.

Regarding question 3 and 4, they studied English Universidad Técnica Nacional during one year in which they experience the effects of technology in a flipped lesson for writing production. They agreed that writing can be a challenging task because of the lack the time it involves producing a piece of writing also, the difficulties of structure and poor vocabulary. For them the writing experience was good, the participants exclaimed that the topics were well developed before the lesson and since the topics were given ahead the explanation and material given by the professor made the process efficient.

Concerning question 5, the use of technology during flipped lessons facilitated the process of creativeness and the understanding of certain rules that were absolutely necessary. The participant C said that even though technology is a great tool for learning, you cannot always rely on it. He stated that technology applied to flipped classroom is a fifty-fifty work. Participant C learned to practice more as well to understand and with the resources, he said that he learned to be more organized.

Participant B stated that the use of technology during writing lessons helped to improve his skills regarding syntax.

Moreover, in question 6, participants expressed how proud they felt about themselves when they wrote in English. They said they felt prepared because of the materials provided and for them the time during class was useful because the professor's attention was focused on the practice. On the other hand, for question 7, they said that they struggled with organization sometimes to find time to study before the lesson and that affected their performance during the class before they could not catch up with other's speed. Participant C and B confessed that for them it was difficult to find time to study the materials sometimes, then the traditional method helped them to catch. Participant A stated that he found himself in a flexible schedule which made him became organized and creative before and during the lesson.

When asked about the effects of technology in flipped classroom for writing production, in question 8, participant A remarked the positiveness of the flipped classroom for interaction with classmates and teacher during the lesson because he did not have to

worry for the materials, and he could study them as many times as he wished. Participant B said that his learning process got better due to the flipped approach because he felt prepared for the exercises and activities. Also, participant C mentioned that blended learning helped him to become independent from teachers and traditional classrooms, now he considers himself his own mentor when there is not anyone to ask.

Finally, for question 9, all the three participants of the focus group considered the flipped classroom with technology in writing courses as a convenient tool to manage time effectiveness and preparation for writing about different topics or writing diverse kind of documents.

b. Likert scale

In regard to the Likert scale the participants were given statements related to the effect they have experienced with technology in flipped classrooms for writing production. The 10 participants that answered the 10 questions. The following are figures that show the results from each of the questions asked in the survey.

Figure 1. Gender

As can be seen in Figure 1, the majority of the participants were male, from 10 participants 6 were men and only 4 of them were women that studied at UTN.

Figure 2. the learning process during flipped lesson

My learning process during the flipped classroom lesson was very good.
10 responses

In the figure 2, we can see that one person did not feel the learning process good, the participant strongly disagrees with the approach, while the other 70 percentage agreed that the learning process during flipped classroom was very good and 20 percentage strongly agreed with it. In other research, learners of 12th grade were in different interaction courses, and most of the class were using the traditional method and while only one classroom was using the flipped method, at the end of the study the outcomes from the flipped classroom were higher than the other courses. All the content was taught simultaneously therefore they did not have advantage over any other course. (Day and Foley 2006).

Figure 3. the use of technology in Flipped classroom improved my writing techniques.

The use of technology in flipped classrooms have help me to improve my writing techniques
10 responses

In the previous figure, the responses from the participants were positive being 20 percentage agreed and 80 percentage strongly agreed with the improvement that the use of technology in flipped classroom brought to their writing techniques. Learners learn the strategy required to develop an ability and to create different and Future Works which that is a successful is technique that requires mental discipline, flexibility, and creative thinking which requires time and peace to work. (Okasha,& Hamdi 2014).

Figure 4. I study more writing when having flipped lessons.

I study more and practice more my writing when having flipped classroom
10 responses

The figure 4 show that 80 percentage of the participants study and practice more their writing when having flipped classrooms, a 10 percentage strongly agreed with that

statement. However, a 10 percentage did not study or practice more when having flipped classrooms. In addition, blended learning facilitates students' listening, speaking, reading, writing and vocabulary development, which echoes previous research findings that implementing blended learning in language courses can significantly improve students' writing knowledge and skills (Shih, 2011; Zheng, 2019) by employing Internet-based learning platforms.

Figure 5. More advantage of time in flipped lessons than in traditional lessons,

For figure 5 variety of responses were given, a 10 percentage did not find more advantage in the flipped lesson than in the traditional. Another 10 percentage choose neutral for both lessons. A 50 percentage find more advantage of time in flipped lessons and the other 30 percentages qualifies time in flipped lesson better spent. Bishop and Verleger (2013), say that free softwares Technologies are related to the growing interest on the flipped classroom models because the free softwares have helped to eliminate some Financial barriers that in some schools that was a problem. Technology is making education more time effective and it has got into the core of the houses of different learners in each place thanks to the different platforms that are being used nowadays.

Figure 6. Characteristic experienced using Technology in Flipped Classrooms.

For the characteristics that learners associated their experience when using technology in a flipped classroom, figure 6 shows that the 6 participants felt innovative, the 10 participants experienced calmness and confidence, 6 of them felt excited and worried, only 2 participants felt stressed and one of the participants experienced frustration. None of them experienced anxiety. Meanwhile, EFL students' learning autonomy, confidence, perseverance and satisfaction are enhanced in a blended learning environment, which is consistent with research that students have greater autonomy in blended learning and they are satisfied with this particular learning model, which prompts greater student perseverance and confidence (Jia et al., 2012; Zhang & Han, 2012).

Figure 7. Development of abilities in writing production positively affected in flipped lessons

My development of abilities in writing production has been positively affected during flipped lessons
10 responses

As can be seen in figure 7, a 30 percentage of the participants stated that their development of abilities was neutral during flipped classroom. A 60 percentage and a 10-percentage stated that their development of abilities in writing production has been positively affected during the blended lessons. Moreover, in the investigation done by Ahmed (2016) explored the effect of a flipping classroom on writing skill in the EFL context of Saudi Arabia with 60 female university learners (30 in flipped classroom and 30 in the control group). The flipped learning group was significantly better than the control group. Furthermore, the participants who experienced flipped learning have positive attitudes towards it.

Figure 8. The use of technology helps the learning process

The use of technology helps me in my learning process

10 responses

In the previous figure 8, the majority of the participant strongly agree that the use of technology helps their learning process. None of them disagreed with the statement. Waxman et al. (2003) stated that research has determined that the implementation of technology into the classroom has a constructive effect on learner academic growth compared with the traditional classroom model.

Figure 9. Students have more time to study in flipped lessons

I have more time to study in flipped classroom

10 responses

The majority of participants, in figure 9, said that they have more time to study in flipped lessons. Only a 10 percentage does not agree with the statement. The benefit of this would be that there is not a time limit on the initial instruction, thus a learner that might learn at a slower rate than their peers would have lots of time to understand a concept,

research it, and practice it without feeling rushed. This would allow them extra time for more mastery, group, and lab practices. (Bishop and Verleger 2013)

Figure 10. Rate of satisfaction in flipped lesson using technology when learning writing production.

What rate of satisfaction would I give to the use of technology in flipped classrooms when learning writing techniques? Being number 1 the lowest rate and 5 the highest rate

10 responses

Finally, in figure 10, 4 participants experienced rate 5 of satisfaction, another 4 experienced rate 4 of satisfaction and only 2 of the experienced rates 3 of satisfaction in flipped lesson using technology for English writing courses. Several studies across a range of disciplines at tertiary institutions have shown promising results with the use of a flipped approach. In some cases, it has been found to produce improved learning outcomes said Peng and Fu (2021), and in many cases it has led to greater student satisfaction (e.g., Enfield, 2013; McGivney-Burelle & Xue, 2013).

Chapter V

Conclusions and Recommendations

5.1 Conclusions

English writing is a challenging task for foreign language learners because the time can be limited. As well as factors like vocabulary and structure also affect the process. The flipped lessons with technology allow to take advantage of time and resource to support the writing process. The participants of the focus group stated that writing can be a challenging task because of the lack the time it involves producing a piece of writing also, the difficulties of structure and poor vocabulary. For them the writing experience was good, the participants exclaimed that the topics were given before class which gave them more time to get ready.

The process of writing becomes efficient when the topic and materials are developed before the lesson. Also, creativity and rule comprehension are understood with ease due to the use of technology simultaneous with the flipped classroom. Consequently, learners get to have more time for practicing their writing skills regarding syntax or soft skills like organization. Peng and Fu (2021) also stated that the results of the descriptive analysis indicate that students' English vocabulary improves the most in blended learning. This suggests that the blended learning model can substantially increase students' vocabulary knowledge by integrating online vocabulary assessment system with face-to-face teaching.

Material provided ahead practice time motivated learners to focus on task requested by teachers. Time gets flexible; therefore, learners organize their schedule according their needs. Learners feel prepared to write in English. Nevertheless, Learners might struggle finding the time to study before class and that causes learners feel behind the other's pace.

In the other hand, interaction among learners and teacher increases while performing tasks as mentioned in Davies et al., (2013). The lesson becomes more effective. In fact, learners learned to be independent from traditional lessons. Inside class, learning may be improved through a greater emphasis on active learning, including problem solving, as well as teachers' ability to focus on students who need extra help (Davies et al., 2013; McGivney-Burelle & Xue, 2013). Learning with this approach allows them to reflect topics. In addition, some characteristics developed using the flipped method for learning in a writing course are mainly innovation, excitement, confidence, and less stress, worries, and frustration. There is research that shows that students have greater autonomy in blended learning, and they are satisfied with this particular learning model, which prompts greater student perseverance and confidence (Jia et al., 2012; Zhang & Han, 2012).

In a summary, the positive effects such as more effective time management, the possibility of more interaction in class to perform practices or get feedback from teachers, besides; the academic growth of student-centered learning while learning vocabulary before writing that according to participants in the survey (See appendix C) with the use of technology was appropriate for the course which caused satisfaction for this approach. In this research, mostly positive are reflected on students while the negative are the minority and they can be fixed through some changes that include reviewing topics or resources before sharing them as well for engaging and effective learning experiences, hands-on activities and in-class cooperative learning can help strengthen team cooperation (Chen & Chen, 2015; Chen et al., 2014).

Furthermore, researchers stated that students engaged in in-class and post class activities. They responded to the different learning approach and were glad to participate in the hands-on activities. For a diversified and seamless learning platform, students' preexisting learning behaviors and interests should be taken into consideration when preparing online teaching according to the research of Shih, W.-L., & Tsai, C.-Y. (2017).. The flipped classroom with technology in writing courses is a convenient tool to manage time effectiveness and preparation for writing about different topics or writing diverse kind of documents.

5.2 Recommendations

There is still a need to further investigate about the performance of technology in writing courses for English language learners, hence; this will allow other English teachers to decide whether or not a tool like technology and its performance would produce in writing courses or in any of the other skills of English learning. The subjects of this study were higher education students of a writing course. Therefore, the result of this study may not be true to all students.

In order to avoid lack of material and vocabulary the learners and teachers can have a section for adding support resources to reinforce the learning process.

Additionally, the type of resources provided to enhance the learning in writing courses has to be reliable before it is sent to learners. As matter of fact, learners need to learn how to implement the flipped method to their different ways of learning. Introductory courses can guide new student in the process.

Another way to help is tutoring for learners who are not at the same pace than others. Learners who are struggling with the learning process using the approach can get a tutor to review and clarify doubts. In this way learners can join the pace of the others without missing the knowledge. Furthermore, proposals for study schedules can be given to students for guidance to find the right time for studying before class.

Moreover, there is a need to focus more on the in-class part of the flipped classroom approach; there were some limited resources of how teachers can motivate and engage students in active participation and critical discussions after the study time before class, as well as how technology can assist in that direction, in this digital era it is fundamental to have reliable sources of information to enhance the lesson we are teaching, as consequence; the future studies should also focus on collecting and triangulating different types of data from different sources to be implemented with technology. Although the reviewed studies have been conducted using a wide range of collected data, ranging from students' attitudes

and other perceptions in other course there is still the need of more research in writing courses implementing the flipped approach, the interpretations and triangulation between the different skills were done to get results, however; the written skill was a challenge for the purpose of this study. For example, issues referring to any writing course that implemented technology with a writing course were limited. For that, it is necessary more research in those aspects mentioned before of flipping the classroom in order to know how to work better and under which circumstances and students.

Finally, the results from the participants cannot be generalized to other English students, nevertheless; this research demonstrates a positive performance in the learning process for writing courses, consequently, it is recommended for teachers to use this strategy with their learners; thus, they can apply it and see if it has a positive performance on their learners as well.

5.3 Proposal

To implement the use of technology in flipped lessons for teaching speaking production in English learners.

As a final proposal, I would like to carry out this project again in the same department of the university but this time with at least 20 participants of a speaking production course, also I would like to create a virtual classroom in google classroom to provide the different technological resources in an easy way to students (See appendix D). With more participants and a different skill, I will be able to obtain more results from different learners. Once the data collecting is finished the outcomes can show if the approach implemented has positive effects on the learning process. The outputs of writing and speaking can be compared and contrasted according to the findings.

For a further implementation of this methodology a webinar can be given to English Professors from Universidad Técnica Nacional, in order to promote and explain the effects of the approach in learners of writing and speaking courses. By sharing this method, more learners and teachers get to experience the effects in order to enhance the learning process. Moreover, it brings more data to be analyzed from different campus and different contexts that might vary from each other.

This proposal can help the Universidad Técnica Nacional to build a richer and more innovate education accessible to everyone. The use of technology in flipped classroom is a challenging approach that can bring many positive effects to the education at UTN classrooms. To conclude, more than proposing an idea, there is a need to develop the strategy, therefore; it can be used in other future courses. There is a sample of the execution of this proposal in the appendix chapter (See appendix D).

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Appendixes

Appendix A: Consent Form

Consent Form

A Case Study: The effects of Technology in flipped classrooms for foreign English language learners of Universidad Técnica Nacional, San Carlos when learning writing production techniques.

By Michelle Ramírez López

Purpose: The purpose of this study is to explore the effects of Technology in flipped classrooms in English as a foreign language learners who have an intermediate English writing proficiency level in the Universidad Técnica Nacional in San Carlos Costa Rica of the Customer Service English program.

I _____ voluntarily agree to participate in this research study.

I understand that even if I agree to participate now, I can withdraw at any time or refuse to answer any question without any consequences of any kind.

I have had the purpose and nature of the study explained to me in writing and I have had the opportunity to ask questions about the study.

I understand that I will not benefit directly from participating in this research. I understand that all information I provide for this study will be treated confidentially.

I agree to my interview being audio-recorded and participate in video calls.

I understand that in any report on the results of this research my identity will remain anonymous. This will be done by changing my name and disguising any details of my interview which may reveal my identity or the identity of people I speak about.

I understand that disguised extracts from my interview may be quoted in the

project.

I understand that signed consent forms and original audio recordings will be retained in hands of the researcher and can be accessed at any time.

I understand that under freedom of information legalization I am entitled to access the information I have provided at any time while it is in storage as specified above.

The participant is giving informed consent to participate in this study

Participant signature _____.

Date _____.

Signature of researcher _____.

Date _____.

Appendix B: Focus Group Interview: First Stage

In the following chart participant will find 9 opened questions regarding the effects of technology in flipped classroom when learning writing production. Participant are encouraged to answer based on their experience at UTN.

1. Tell me about yourself?
2. For how long have you been studying English?
3. Is writing in English a challenge for you in classes?
4. Tell me your experience in the writing production classes at UTN?
5. What did it feel like to use technology for a writing production class?
6. What stood out to you as the defining characteristics of your writing lessons?
7. As a student at UTN during the time, Did you observe any specific action developed in your writing skills when the use of technology or online materials was provided before class?
8. How has the flipped lessons affected your learning process?
9. Would you define flipped classroom as a positive or negative methodology for the writing courses?

Appendix C: Survey Likert scale: Second Stage

In the following survey, you will read ten statements in a Likert scale the participants related to the effects they have experienced with technology in flipped classrooms for writing production.

The effects of Technology in flipped classrooms for foreign English language learners of Universidad Técnica Nacional, San Carlos when learning writing production techniques.

We are conducting research in which our goal is to explore the effect through research. The survey should only take 10 minutes, and your responses are completely anonymous. The information provided here is for educational purposes only.

If you have any questions about the survey, please email us: micheramirezl@email.com

We really appreciate your participation. Thank you.

* Required

1. Gender *

Mark only one oval.

Female

Male

2. My learning process during the flipped classroom lesson was very good. *

Mark only one oval.

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neutral

Agree

Strongly agree

3. The use of technology in flipped classrooms have help me to improve my writing techniques *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
 Disagree
 Neutral
 Agree
 Strongly Agree

4. I study more and practice more my writing when having flipped classroom

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly Disagree
 Disagree
 Neutral
 Agree
 Strongly Agree

5. I take more advantage of time in flipped lessons than in traditional lessons *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
 Disagree
 Neutral
 Agree
 Strongly agree

6. Choose the characteristics you have experienced when using technology in a flipped classroom. *

Check all that apply.

- innovative
- Excited
- calm
- confident
- Stress
- Anxiety
- worried
- Frustrated

7. My development of abilities in writing production has been positively affected during flipped lessons *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

8. The use of technology helps me in my learning process *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

9. I have more time to study in flipped classroom *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly agree

10. What rate of satisfaction would I give to the use of technology in flipped classrooms when learning writing techniques? Being number 1 the lowest rate and 5 the highest rate *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Lowest	<input type="radio"/>	Highest				

Appendix D: Tool for proposal

The design of a virtual space in google classroom to post material ahead class for the flipped approach:

The screenshot displays the Google Classroom interface for a course titled "English Journey Group 6". The "Classwork" tab is selected, showing a list of assignments. The interface includes a navigation bar at the top with "Stream", "Classwork", "People", and "Grades" tabs. A sidebar on the left shows "Week 1" and "General Course Info...". The main content area lists assignments under "Week 1" and "General Course Information".

Assignment	Posted/Edited
session 1	Posted Aug 23
session 4	Posted Aug 23
session 3	Posted Aug 23
session 2	Posted Aug 23
Session 1	Posted Aug 16
Course Chronogram	Edited Aug 23
Course program	Posted Aug 16

